

WELCOME TO OUR JOINT EXTERNAL NEWSLETTER #5

1,430 FARMS REGISTERED, ACHIEVING 98% OF OUR TARGET!

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Recruiting almost 1,500 farms was a real challenge and not an easy one - especially during this period of turmoil in the agricultural sector throughout Europe - but we did it all together! This major step has been taken and will enable us to consolidate our actions on the ground to promote and massively disseminate a whole range of Climate Smart Farming Practices within European farming communities.

Christine Berger
Climate Farm Demo Project Coordinator

CLIMATE FARM DEMO'S DIGITAL REPOSITORY: A MILESTONE IN AGRICULTURAL SUSTAINABILITY

Aiming beyond Climate Farm Demo, we're creating a EU-wide climate knowledge repository to centralize resources and unite stakeholders. Celebrating the Digital Repository's launch, we encourage all in the agri-food sector to explore this hub for sustainable agricultural progress. Led by the Agricultural University of Athens and partners, this groundbreaking platform is a leap towards carbon-neutral farming in Europe. Starting with a survey that collected 34 tools and growing through a literature review to 125 Knowledge Objects, it's more than a database—it's a dynamic resource for climate-smart agriculture. Dive into a wealth of tools, models, and methods all aimed at empowering the agricultural sector with solutions for climate change mitigation and adaptation.

[CHECK OUT THE REPOSITORY HERE](#)

KEY INSIGHTS AND TRENDS

The repository is a comprehensive collection of tools for climate and carbon management in agriculture, showcasing accessibility, and farm-level applicability.

PLATFORM INTEGRATION AND USER-FRIENDLY INTERFACE

Integrated into the project's site and crafted by BIOS, it offers an intuitive design and efficient filtering, enabling easy access to its rich knowledge for the agri-food sector.

EMPOWERING CLIMATE ACTION: LUSIGNAN'S GATHERING OF LIVING LABS

Representatives from all 10 Living Labs convened in Lusignan, France two weeks ago for an enriching exchange. Wageningen University & Research, ILVO and Universidad de Almería hosted interactive workshops to refine climate-smart measures and share experiences. A special thanks to the INRAE team for their invaluable facilitation of the meeting!

They exchanged insights, got hands-on with design thinking, put monitoring and evaluation into action, and left brimming with inspiration for the next phase.

Each Living Lab collaborates closely with stakeholders to bridge the gap between research and practical applications, ensuring real-world impact.

[LEARN MORE ABOUT LIVING LABS HERE](#)

INTEGRATING REWARDING MECHANISMS INTO THE FABRIC OF OUR LIVING LABS

WP4's Living Labs collaborating with WP6's rewarding mechanisms emphasizes our commitment to sustainability and innovation, aiming to enhance co-creation with incentives for sustainable climate solutions.

NAVIGATING THE FUTURE WITH CLIMATE FARM DEMO'S PIP STRATEGIC PLAN

The Climate Farm Demo project sets the pace with a dynamic Strategic Plan by CONSULAI, charting a six-year path to integrate Projects, Initiatives, and Policymakers (PIPs) with our mission.

More than a plan, it's a flexible commitment, with yearly adjustments by Work Package 7 ensuring alignment with our goals and the evolving agricultural sector. As we move forward, we welcome contributions from partners to keep our strategy vibrant and impactful.

EMPOWERING A GREENER FUTURE: LAUNCH OF THE FIRST CLIMATESMARTADVISORS TTT IN DUBLIN

From March 19-22, 2024, the Teagasc College of Amenity Horticulture hosted a pivotal gathering where 40 Coaches and Advisors from 27 European countries honed their climate change strategies for sustainable agriculture, as part of the ClimateSmartAdvisors project.

The workshop prioritized Communities of Practice (CoPs), led by diverse experts, covering CoP management, climate-smart advisory services, and practical agricultural strategies.

Participants received advanced facilitation training, fostering a substantial exchange of tailored knowledge and strategies, empowering advisors to champion sustainable farming practices across Europe.

Now, our Coaches and Advisors are launching their own CoPs in their countries, embarking on a two-year journey as part of the project's first CoP wave. Thank you to all involved for making the TTT a resounding success!

[CLICK HERE TO READ MORE](#)

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Teagasc was delighted to host the 40 advisors from across Europe for this training event. It was a great opportunity for advisors to learn new skills and to meet advisors from other European countries who are all supporting farmers in reducing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture. Using the skills acquired, the advisors can take a lead in developing the capacity of many more advisors across Europe.

*Tom O'Dwyer
Head of Signpost Programme, Teagasc*

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